

www.bjisrd.com

Glossary - a Method for Forming Thematic Dictionaries

Mukimova Gulandom Axatovna

Teacher of the Russian language department and literature Faculty of Philology Bukhara State University

***Annotation:** The article discusses the method of compiling thematic dictionaries and the form of compiling a glossary. The glossary is an effective means of word interpretation, commentary, examples and translation. The properties of a glossary are that it can be supplemented as they stay.*

***Keywords:** Glossary, dictionaries, microlevel, macrolevel, literature, terminology, interpretation, translation, word meaning, professionalism.*

As you know, a glossary (lat. "Glossarium" - "dictionary", "gloss") is a dictionary of specialized terms in a specific branch of knowledge, sometimes with interpretation, comments, examples and translation. The latter type of glossaries is indispensable for a practicing translator. It is a necessary tool to ensure and improve the quality of translation. Glossaries are different - officially published and professionally compiled, amateur and unsystematic, and they have a common purpose - to help the translator in his difficult work. The prototype of the glossary appeared a very long time ago (back in the 25th century BC) in the form of the meanings of foreign and rare words (glossa) written on the margins of ancient manuscripts. Before the era of typography, handwritten glossaries were quickly copied and distributed, and when the first books appeared, glossaries were among them. In the 20th century, to fulfill large translation orders, one translator or a group of translators always used the glossaries compiled by them in paper form. In our century, as a rule, glossaries are compiled, stored, updated and used in electronic form. Working with glossaries can be roughly divided into two levels: micro and macro levels. The micro-level involves the compilation of personal glossaries - when the translator studies the literature on a specific topic and searches for equivalents of frequently used phrases and expressions. Why is it necessary to compile glossaries? In many languages, the meaning of the same word can be conveyed by different words or phrases, the meaning of which can be very different. In a number of situations, such variations are unacceptable, for example, in working with scientific and technical literature: an incorrectly chosen term in translation can distort the meaning of the entire document. Therefore, to ensure uniformity of terminology, translators compile special lists of terms (glossaries), carefully checking their correctness in published international or national guidelines, standards and specialized

dictionaries. Thus, glossaries help to keep possible translation inaccuracies to a minimum. This is extremely important, since the cost of a translator's error can be very high - for example, difficulties in the work of specialists following incorrectly translated instructions, and the damaged reputation of the translator himself. Glossaries are often written for a new topic or area of expertise, as you need to stock up on proven equivalents from the start. In addition, glossaries are especially useful when the subject of translation is periodically repeated. A glossary saves time that would otherwise be spent re-familiarizing yourself with the topic of the translation. As a rule, the need to compile a glossary arises when working with large texts, as well as when a group of translators is simultaneously working on the translation of one document or translation project. In such cases, the glossary helps to use the same terms throughout the text, regardless of how many people translated, thus minimizing the "human factor". The customer may have already established basic terms that differ slightly from the generally accepted terms in this area. They should also be added to the glossary. In addition, the glossary, as necessary, includes definitions and interpretations of terms, examples of their use depending on the situation. Glossaries can contain various elements of the language: from abbreviations and words to individual phrases, sentences and paragraphs (for example, slogans, professional jargon, product descriptions, etc.). We believe that a separate glossary should be compiled for each document containing specialized terminology, acronyms, abbreviations and expressions. In addition to the consistency of terms, it is also necessary to maintain a consistent translation style. Compiling a glossary is a complex and time-consuming process. A glossary can be written both in the process of translation, from scratch, replenished in the course of work, and by comparing parallel, already translated, texts manually or using special programs.

The micro-level involves the compilation of personal glossaries - when the translator studies the literature on a specific topic and searches for equivalents of frequently used phrases and expressions. Why is it necessary to compile glossaries? In many languages, the meaning of the same word can be conveyed by different words or phrases, the meaning of which can be very different. In a number of situations, such variations are unacceptable, for example, in working with scientific and technical literature: an incorrectly chosen term in translation can distort the meaning of the entire document. Therefore, to ensure uniformity of terminology, translators compile special lists of terms (glossaries), carefully checking their correctness in published international or national guidelines, standards and specialized dictionaries. Thus, glossaries help to keep possible translation inaccuracies to a minimum. This is extremely important, since the cost of a translator's error can be very high - for example, difficulties in the work of specialists following incorrectly translated instructions, and the damaged reputation of the translator himself. Glossaries are often written for a new topic or area of expertise, as you need to stock up on proven equivalents from the start. In addition, glossaries are especially useful when the subject of translation is periodically repeated. A glossary saves time that would otherwise be spent re-familiarizing yourself with the topic of the translation. As a rule, the need to compile a glossary arises when working with large texts, as well as when a group of translators is simultaneously working on the translation of one document or translation project. In such cases, the glossary helps to use the same terms throughout the text, regardless of how many people translated, thus minimizing the "human factor". The customer may have already established basic terms that differ slightly from the generally accepted terms in this area. They should also be added to the glossary. In addition, the glossary, as necessary, includes definitions and interpretations of terms, examples of their use depending on the situation. Glossaries can contain various elements of the language: from abbreviations and words to individual phrases, sentences and paragraphs (for example, slogans, professional jargon, product descriptions, etc.). We believe that a separate glossary should be compiled for each document containing specialized terminology, acronyms, abbreviations and expressions. In

addition to the consistency of terms, it is also necessary to maintain a consistent translation style. Compiling a glossary is a complex and time-consuming process. A glossary can be written both in the process of translation, from scratch, replenished in the course of work, and by comparing parallel, already translated, texts manually or using special programs.

The translator, having studied this document, will not make mistakes when translating the phrase “gender budgeting” and translates as “genderbudgeting”, “readiness to move to e-government” as “e-governmentreadiness”, and “logrolling” as “ system of mutual services ”. It is expected that this collection will be regularly reviewed and updated. In addition to the separately published glossaries, there are electronic glossary systems that are also very convenient. The most famous of these is the United Nations multilingual terminology database UNTERM (<http://unterm.un.org>). The system contains several hundred thousand entries in the six official languages of the United Nations and is an indispensable resource for a translator. It contains cross-references and an indication of a list of related concepts for each term used in official UN documents. This database can be very useful in identifying translations of the most commonly used terms in all six official languages of the United Nations. The above glossaries allow the translator to search for equivalents already published, i.e. "Precedents" in previously issued documents. They help to improve the quality of the translator's work and achieve consistency between a translation or a series of translations on the same subject. A personal glossary is a kind of indicator of the translator's professionalism: its level directly depends on how often it is replenished and in what state it is. Thus, a glossary is a useful tool that allows a translator to easily find the required equivalent, avoid inaccuracies when working with specialized terminology and continuously improve the quality of his work - both in the process of compiling and using ready-made glossaries.

Literature

1. Olimov, Shirinboy Sharofovich. "THE INNOVATION PROCESS IS A PRIORITY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES." (2021).
2. Saydaliyev, S., & Gulomova, N. (2019). Development of Spatial Thinking of Students Based on the Traditions of Eastern Architecture. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies*, 14(2), 210-214.
3. Saydaliyev, S. S., & Gulomova, N. K. (2015). Umumiy O „Rta Ta“Lim Muassasalarida Tasviriy San“At Darslarini Sifat Va Samaradorligining Oshirish. *Formation A Culture Of Independent Thinking In The Educational Process*, 161.
4. Avezova D. SPEAKING SURNAMES AND THEIR ROLE IN THE STYLISTIC IMAGE OF A WORK OF ART //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. C10. – C. 59-62.
5. Авезова Д. METHODS OF TEACHING THE MORPHOLOGY OF THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE TO STUDENTS NON-LINGUISTIC DIRECTIONS //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2023. – Т. 42. – №. 42.